

Optimization of 14 nm double gate Bi-GFET for lower leakage current

Nur Hazwani Naili Mohd Nizam¹, Afifah Maheran Abdul Hamid¹, Fauziyah Salehuddin¹,
Khairil Ezwan Kaharudin², Noor Faizah Zainul Abidin³, Anis Suhaila Mohd Zain¹

¹MiNE, Faculty of Electronics and Computer Engineering, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), Hang Tuah Jaya, Durian Tunggal, 76100 Melaka, Malaysia

²Electrical and Electronics, Faculty of Engineering, Lincoln University College Main Campus, Selangor Darul Ehsan, Malaysia

³Engineering and Technology, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Spectrum International College of Technology, The Main Place Mall, Jalan USJ21/10, USJ 21, 47360 Subang Jaya, Selangor, Malaysia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Feb 28, 2022

Revised Nov 18, 2022

Accepted Nov 28, 2022

Keywords:

Bilayer graphene

Double gate MOSFET

High-k/metal gate

Leakage current

Taguchi

ABSTRACT

In recent years, breakthroughs in electronics technology have upgraded the physical properties of the metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistor (MOSFET) toward smaller sizes and improvements in both quality and performance. Hence, the growth field effect transistor (GFET) is being promoted as one of the worthy candidates due to its superior material characteristics. A 14 nm horizontal double-gate bilayer graphene field effect transistor (FET) utilizing high-k and a metal gate, which are composed of hafnium dioxide (HfO_2) and tungsten silicide (WSi_x) respectively. Silvaco ATHENA and ATLAS technology computer-aided design (TCAD) tools are used to simulate the design and electrical properties, while Taguchi L9 orthogonal arrays (OA) are used to optimize the electrical properties. The threshold voltage (V_{TH}) adjustment implant dose, V_{TH} adjustment implant energy, source/drain (S/D) implant dose, and S/D implant energy have all been investigated as process parameters, while the V_{TH} adjustment tilt angle and the S/D implant tilt angle have been investigated as noise factors. When compared to the initial findings before optimization, the I_{OFF} has a value of 29.579 nA/ μm , indicating a significant improvement. Findings from the optimization technique demonstrate excellent device performance with an I_{OFF} of 28.564 nA/ μm , which is closer to the international technology roadmap for semiconductors (ITRS) 2013 target.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Afifah Maheran Abdul Hamid

MiNE, Faculty of Electronics and Computer Engineering, Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM)

Hang Tuah Jaya, Durian Tunggal, 76100 Melaka, Malaysia

Email: afifah@utem.edu.my

1. INTRODUCTION

For the past five decades, the scaling down of complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) technology has been completely achieved by scaling down their physical dimensions and increasing device switching speed in accordance with Moore's law. Thus, maintaining the off-state power consumption for metal oxide semiconductor (MOS) devices became exceedingly challenging [1], [2]. Advanced CMOS technology is moving toward the development of shorter, thinner gate oxides. Smaller channel thicknesses are preferred to reduce drain-induced barrier lowering. However, the quantum effects limit the channel thickness selection. This leads to a substantial rise in quantum effects next to the silicon interface, which is primarily responsible for the carrier charge distribution in the channel, particularly in the inversion rule of the channel.

To accurately simulate a metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistor (MOSFET), all of these factors must be taken into consideration. When charge carriers are quantized in the continuous energy band, they must be transferred from the valence band to the conduction band, increasing the required gate voltage. In this scenario, the quantum mechanical (QM) phenomenon takes place, and as a result of this quantization phenomenon, the threshold voltage of the device increases [3]–[7]. Another design used to address the short channel effect (SCE) problems is the double gate (DG) MOSFET architecture [8]. It is because by raising the number of gates in the channel, the electrostatic regulation of the channel is improved, and the short-channel effects are decreased. Short-channel effects occur as a result of the impact of the electric field flowing from source to drain on the control of the gate channel. The multi-gate MOSFET is a good choice because it can deal with short-channel effects and keep the device stable [4]. The double gate MOSFET has faster switching operation than planar MOSFETs. Since it can be driven independently, the double gate MOSFET is frequently seen as being desirable in power applications [9], [10]. When compared to silicon, graphene is described as a crystalline allotrope of carbon with two-dimensional properties. It is considered to be the most attractive candidate since it has higher electron mobility, higher current capability and is less dense [11], [12]. Despite its excellent electrical properties, graphene field-effect transistors (GFETs) are still challenging to use in digital logic because graphene does not have a band gap in its normal state, making the field effect transistor (FETs) difficult to switch off. The only known material with an adjustable band gap is bilayer graphene, which is composed of two layers of carbon [13].

Leakage current (I_{OFF}) in a device is a crucial electrical characteristic to consider in device characterization, design, and circuit design since device downscaling has brought the drain area significantly closer to the source [14]. The increase in leakage current is believed to be triggered by changes in process parameters. According to a previous study, the temperature can affect ionic current, causing an increase in off-state current and a decrease in the I_{ON}/I_{OFF} current ratio, and it can also affect leakage current, causing an increase in leakage current due to the increase in heating current [15]. The process parameters employed in the design process, such as the V_{TH} adjustment implantation, the threshold voltage (V_{TH}) energy, the source/drain (S/D) implantation, and the S/D energy, must be optimized for a robust design. Various different input process characteristics need to be examined in order to identify the leakage current's (I_{OFF}) main causes. High-k dielectric materials are suggested as a gate oxide control strategy to deal with the excess I_{OFF} problem. To solve the issue of excessive I_{OFF} , it is being explored to introduce high-k dielectric materials as one of the gate oxide management solutions. Additionally, a high-k dielectric can be used to achieve a larger gate capacitance at a greater thickness [16], [17].

It has been discovered that hafnium dioxide (HfO_2) serves as a high-k dielectric material, and tungsten silicide (WSi_x) serve as a metal gate. HfO_2 is considered to be the most ideal high-k dielectric material for gate oxides because it exhibits the least amount of gate leakage and the highest performance when dealing with short channel effects such as subthreshold swings (SS), leakage current (I_{OFF}), and I_{ON}/I_{OFF} ratio, among others. Traditional polysilicon/silicon dioxide (poly-Si/ SiO_2) technology might still be used in small-scaled MOSFET devices to meet the International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors (ITRS) 2013 requirements for low power (LP) technology. However, conventional poly-Si/ SiO_2 technology is no longer practical because short channel effects and poly depletion effects degrade transistor performance below the 22 nm technology node. Furthermore, since silicon dioxide (SiO_2) has a higher subthreshold leakage than HfO_2 , its leakage is bigger HfO_2 [18]. Due to the obvious high dielectric constant of HfO_2 , it has been proposed as a potential high-k material [19], [20]. A decrease in the amount of gate voltage required to increase the drain current has been achieved by using WSi_x and HfO_2 as substitutes for polysilicon and SiO_2 , respectively [21]. The thickness variation of the pillar is essentially nonexistent in a high-k/metal-gate design since there are no effects on polysilicon depletion. Since WSi_x is compatible with both negative channel metal oxide semiconductor (NMOS) and positive channel metal oxide semiconductor (PMOS) devices, the metal-gate work-function engineering patent facilitates its usage as a metal gate. WSi_x is believed to have a variety of applications and strong thermal stability and conductivity [17], [22].

The Silvaco application programme, as well as the ATHENA and ATLAS modules, were used to simulate the manufacturing process of virtual devices and analyse their electrical properties [23]. For optimising the process parameters to achieve a robust design at the lowest possible cost, the Taguchi approach is a crucial factor to consider. In a certain process or design, the Taguchi technique, also known as the optimal input process parameter values, can be used to identify the ideal input process parameter values to be used. The Taguchi approach was chosen for this investigation because of its time efficiency and high durability [24]. Various researchers have successfully used the L9 orthogonal array (OA) Taguchi technique to improve process parameters in order to achieve the lowest I_{OFF} , as anticipated in the ITRS 2013 report [25]–[27].

2. METHODOLOGY

It was conceivable to construct a 14 nm horizontal double gate n-channel bilayer graphene with a high-k/metal gate by using the ATHENA module of the Silvaco technology computer-aided design (TCAD) tools while the ATLAS module of the Silvaco TCAD tools was used to acquire the electrical properties of the device. The fabrication step uses the same current top transistor well-matched procedure to produce results that satisfy traditional ITRS requirements while varying a number of design factors, including doping density, energy, and tilt angle. It is used in this area of the device to dope boron at a dosage of 1.0×10^{14} ions/cm³ and to dope a silicon substrate with an orientation of $\langle 100 \rangle$, which is 8 nm in size and *p*-type. The threshold voltage adjustment is carried out in the channel area of the transistor using a boron dose of 1.13×10^{13} cm³ at 20 KeV and a tilt of 10°. A bilayer graphene material with a thickness of 1 nm and a length of 24 nm was then deposited on top of the silicon layer, and the process was repeated. HfO₂ with a permittivity of 25 was used in this study [28]. A 2 nm thick layer of HfO₂ was placed on top of bilayer graphene with a length of 24 nm, which was followed by the deposition of a WSi_x with a 3 nm thick layer. After that, etching is employed to achieve the necessary thickness, and the gate length of 14 nm is accomplished. It was determined that the WSi_x gate would have a 4.5 eV metal-gate work function. For the source drain implant, arsenic was administered at a dose of 1×10^{17} at a frequency of 2 KeV tilted at 77° at a dose of 1×10^{17} cm³. After that, a coating of aluminum was added to the structure, and any excess aluminum was etched aside. This allowed the contacts to be formed. Once the transistor has been exposed to the electrical characterization procedure using the ATLAS simulation module, it is possible to determine and examine the threshold voltage of the transistor in relation to ITRS. The value of the I_{OFF} must be lower than 100 nm for the 14 nm gate length in order for the device to function properly [29]. The summarized for the simulation recipe of 14 nm NMOS horizontal double gate is shown in Table 1.

Four control factors and two noise factors were selected for this study based on the findings of previous research and were tested [30]. The control factors in this study are the threshold voltage (V_{TH}) adjustment implant dose, threshold voltage (V_{TH}) adjustment implant energy, S/D)implant dose and S/D implant energy while the noise factors are S/D implant tilt angle and threshold voltage (V_{TH}) adjustment tilt angle. Table 2 shows the values of each parameter at various levels, while Table 3 shows the noise factors for *n*-type MOSFETs.

Table 1. Horizontal double gate fabrication recipe

Process step	<i>n</i> -type MOSFET parameters
Silicon substrate	$\langle 100 \rangle$ orientation
V_{th} adjust implant	1.13e13cm ³ Boron Dose 20 KeV implant energy 10° tilt 30 rotations
Bilayer graphene deposition	Thickness: 0.001 μm length: 0.024 μm
High-k/metal gate deposition	HfO ₂ thickness: 0.002 μm HfO ₂ length: 0.024 μm WSi _x thickness: 0.05 μm WSi _x length: 0.014 μm
Source/drain implantation	1e17cm ³ implantation dose 2 KeV implant energy 77° tilt 60 rotations
Aluminium deposition	0.016 μm

Table 2. Process parameters and their levels

Symbol	Process parameter	Unit	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
A	V_{TH} adjustment implant dose	Atom/cm ³	1.03×10^{13}	1.13×10^{13}	1.23×10^{13}
B	V_{TH} adjustment implant energy	KeV	18	20	22
C	S/D implant dose	Atom/cm ³	0.8×10^{17}	1×10^{17}	1.2×10^{17}
D	S/D implant energy	KeV	1.8	2	2.2

Table 3. Noise factors and their levels

Symbol	Noise factor	Unit	Level 1	Level 2
X	V_{TH} adjustment implant tilt	Degree	10	12
Y	S/D implant tilt	Degree	77	79

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Fabrication Simulation Result

A set of software tools from Silvaco TCAD was used to conduct electrical characterization of the 14 nm *n*-channel horizontal double gate bilayer graphene field effect transistor (Bi-GFET). In Figure 1, Silvaco ATHENA is used to display the completed device for a 14 nm *n*-type horizontal double gate MOSFET with a bilayer graphene/high-*k*/metal gate. The device is shown in its completed form since it has been constructed. Due to the obvious change in the design of the gate, the amount of doping introduced into the device has changed because of the change in design. Figure 1 shows the silicon, graphene, high-*k*/metal gate, and aluminium configurations of the 14 nm NMOS horizontal double gate MOSFET design in 14 nm HfO₂/WSi_x technology. Figure 2 shows material measurements of the device, and Figure 3 shows the doping profile of the 14 nm NMOS horizontal double gate MOSFET design.

Figure 1. The measurement of the material in 14 nm horizontal double gate of NMOS transistor

Figure 2. The doping profile of 14 nm double gate NMOS

3.2. Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) analysis

Using the Taguchi L9 orthogonal array approach researchers were able to achieve the lower leakage current predicted by ITRS 2013. In this experiment, the smaller the grade attributes of the I_{OFF} , the better the grade attributes. The following stage was to discover the control parameters that have the greatest impact on the device features in order to have a better knowledge of the device characteristics. One of the steps is the analysis of the experiment's SNR. In this experiment, the I_{OFF} analysis is referred to as SNR smaller the better (STB), and the purpose of the analysis is to determine the amount of control factors that result in an outcome value that is as near to as possible to the predicted value by ITRS 2013, which is less than 100 nm in this experiment. When the signal to noise ratio of a process parameter is the highest, it is assumed that the factor has a stronger signal than the combination of the random effects of the noise factors. The best lowest quality characteristic type was chosen in this investigation to achieve the lowest I_{OFF} value predicted by ITRS. As indicated in Table 4 below, the L9 orthogonal array approach was used to optimize the I_{OFF} of the NMOS transistor, and the outcomes of this optimization are displayed.

Next, compute the factor effect percentage on SNR for NMOS transistors. The SNR of each level of the process parameter for I_{OFF} is outlined in Table 5. The Table 5 impact comes to illustrate that S/D implant energy (D) has the most elevated impact on minimizing I_{OFF} esteem within the NMOS device, with 94.09%, followed by S/D implant dose (C) with 4.82%. On the other hand, V_{TH} adjustment implant energy (B) only gives a 0.62% effect on the device, followed by the V_{TH} adjustment implant dose (A) with 0.46%.

Table 4. Result for I_{OFF} value based on L9 orthogonal array

Exp no.	Leakage current, I_{OFF} (nA/ μ m)				Overall mean	SNR
	X1, Y1	X1, Y2	X2, Y1	X2, Y2		
1	30.566	30.678	30.565	30.677	150.56	150.28
2	29.614	29.672	29.609	29.667		150.56
3	28.885	28.926	28.875	28.915		150.78
4	28.825	28.853	28.815	28.841		150.80
5	30.211	30.306	30.209	30.304		150.38
6	29.815	29.883	29.811	29.879		150.50
7	29.339	29.386	29.334	29.380		150.65
8	29.048	29.086	29.041	29.078		150.73
9	30.374	30.476	30.372	30.475		150.34

Table 5. SNR of each level of process parameters

Process parameter	SNR (dB)			Factor effect on SNR (%)
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	
V _{TH} adjustment implant dose	150.54	150.56	150.57	0.46
V _{TH} adjustment implant energy	150.58	150.56	150.54	0.62
S/D implant dose	150.50	150.57	150.60	4.82
S/D implant energy	150.33	150.57	150.77	94.09

Figure 3 shows factor effect plot of control factor levels for signal noise ratio smaller the better (SNR STB) in decibel (dB). On the graph shown, the dotted boundaries represent the values of the total mean of SNR (STB) which is 150.56 dB. Each process parameter’s level value is shown on the graph as well. From the left, V_{TH} adjustment implant dose (factor A), V_{TH} adjustment implant energy (factor B), S/D implant dose (factor C) and S/D implant energy (factor D) are all shown in the graphs, with the slopes corresponding to each of them.

Figure 3. Factor effect plot for SNR (smaller the better)

3.2.1. Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

The variance (ANOVA) of the input process parameters is a commonly used statistical method for determining which of those input process parameters appears to have a significant impact on the performance character trait during an investigation [31]. The standard deviation of the experimental tests is used to determine the standard deviation of the experimental data from the mean value of data in data analysis. Table 6 displays the results of the ANOVA for the device under consideration. As a percentage of the factor effect on SNR, SNR shows which process parameters are most critical. In terms of the effect of factors on SNR, the influence of the Table 6 shows that S/D implant energy (D) has the most impact on reducing I_{OFF} esteem within the NMOS device with 94.09%. At present, S/D implant dose (C) has the largest instantaneous highest effect with 4.82%, followed by V_{TH} adjustment implant energy (B) with 0.62%, and lastly, V_{TH} adjustment implant dose (A) has the least percentage that gives effect to the device with 0.02%.

Table 6. Results of ANOVA for I_{OFF}

Process parameter	Factor effect on SNR (%)
V _{TH} adjustment implant dose	0.46
V _{TH} adjustment implant energy	0.62
S/D implant dose	4.82
S/D implant energy	94.09

Table 7. Best setting parameter for I_{OFF}

Symbol	Process parameter	Level	Best value (atom/cm ³)
A	V _{TH} adjustment implant dose	3	1.23X10 ¹³
B	V _{TH} adjustment implant energy	1	18
C	S/D implant dose	3	1.20X10 ¹⁷
D	S/D implant energy	3	2.2

3.2.2. Confirmation test

The optimum process parameter levels predicted by the L9 orthogonal array (OA) of the Taguchi technique were used to re-simulate the 14 nm Bi-GFET horizontal double gate device, as Table 7. The Table 7 shows the optimal process parameter levels. The SNR (mean) value with the highest value is the ideal level for device design in the event of I_{OFF}. According to the finalized standards, levels A3, B1, C3, and D3 are the finalized specifications for an I_{OFF} built exclusively for NMOS devices. Based on the Taguchi approach, Table 8 shows

the optimal anticipated Taguchi method setting for the I_{OFF} process parameter combination. Using these final numbers and the noise factor, Table 8 displays the optimal I_{OFF} result with the lowest feasible value. Following the last step in the process to improve the noise factor parameter, the results with the I_{OFF} value are lower than the results with the ITRS prediction value.

Table 8. Confirmation results for I_{OFF} using L9 OA of Taguchi method

I_{OFF} 1(nA/ μ m) X1, Y1	I_{OFF} 2(nA/ μ m) X1, Y2	I_{OFF} 3(nA/ μ m) X2, Y1	I_{OFF} 4(nA/ μ m) X2, Y2
28.576	28.593	28.564	28.579

As another researcher of 14 nm have been reported was planar MOSFET design and fin field effect transistor (FinFET) design technology [32], [33]. According to ITRS 2013, the leakage current for 14 nm must be less than 100 nm, and this research revealed that the value of 28.564 nm is in accordance with ITRS 2013, indicating that the value is in line with ITRS 2013. When it comes to parameter optimization, the Taguchi technique is widely accepted. In this case, the Taguchi approach was used in the design of a 14 nm n -type MOSFET to achieve the lowest possible value of the I_{OFF} predicted by the ITRS. Throughout this finding, it was discovered that S/D implant energy (D) has the highest impact on decreasing I_{OFF} esteem within the NMOS device, with a reduction of 94.19% compared to base. Thus, minor changes in the energy of the S/D implant would have a significant impact on the I_{OFF} value. Table 9 shows the leakage current simulation results of 14 nm Bi-GFET horizontal double gate after optimize using Taguchi L9.

Table 9. Simulation results of 14 nm Bi-GFET horizontal double gate

Performance parameter	ITRS prediction	Non-optimized results	Optimized result
		29.579	28.564
I_{OFF} (nA/ μ m)	<100	Reduction value (%)	
		70.421	71.436

4. CONCLUSION

Consequently, using Silvaco ATHENA and ATLAS TCAD tools, the proposed structure of a 14 nm gate length horizontal double gate bilayer graphene field effect transistor with a high-k dielectric function and a metal gate HfO_2/WSi_x was simulated and modeled. The finalized layout was then optimized using Taguchi L9 OA. Prior to optimization, the results for the horizontal double gate design were 29.579 nm, with a reduced value of 70.431%, while the optimized results were 28.564, with a better reduction value of 71.436%, while the I_{OFF} value for the planar design from the earlier study is higher than the double gate, which is 77.11 nm. According to the author's knowledge, this study is the first to utilize a bi-layer graphene, high-k, metal gate, and horizontal double gate MOSFET and optimize by using L9 orthogonal array of the Taguchi method on a 14 nm device.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors appreciate the moral and operational assistance they received from the MiNE, CeTRI, FKEKK, UTeM, and the Ministry of Higher Education during the project. The funding for this publication comes from the FRGS/1/2020/FKEKK-CETRI/F00427 grant.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Bhattacharya and S. L. Tripathi, "A novel junction less dual gate tunnel FET with SiGe pocket for low power applications," in *2021 Devices for Integrated Circuit (DevIC)*, 2021, pp. 479–483, doi: 10.1109/DevIC50843.2021.9455807.
- [2] S. Bhattacharya and S. L. Tripathi, "Implementation of low power inverter using $Si_{1-x}Ge_x$ pocket N & P-channel junction-less double gate TFET," *Silicon*, vol. 14, pp. 9129–9142, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12633-021-01628-w.
- [3] H. Abebe and E. Cumberbatch, "Modeling quantum effects on MOSFET channel surface potential," in *Proceedings 2004 International Conference on Computing, Communications and Control Technologies: CCCT04*, 2004, vol. 7, pp. 14–17. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286457739_Modeling_Quantum_Effects_on_MOSFET_Channel_Surface_Potential
- [4] S. S. J. P. Bantupalli, P. ArunaPriya, T. Sharma, and R. HariPrasad, "Modelling of multigate MOSFET short channel structure for low power application," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2021, vol. 1964, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1964/6/062017.
- [5] S. Jha and S. K. Choudhary, "A comparative analysis of the short-channel effects of double-gate, tri-gate and gate-all-around MOSFETs," *International Journal of Nanoparticles*, vol. 12, no. 1-2, pp. 112–121, 2020, doi: 10.1504/IJNP.2020.106002.
- [6] Y. Lv, Y. Liu, L. Liao, W. Qin, and C. Jiang, "Electronic fluctuation of graphene nanoribbon MOSFETs under a full quantum dynamics framework," *IEEE Transactions on Electron Devices*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 1980–1985, 2021, doi: 10.1109/TED.2021.3060347.
- [7] M. S. -Jelodar, S. Kim, K. Ng, and G. Klimeck, "Transistor roadmap projection using predictive full-band atomistic modeling," *Applied Physics Letters*, vol. 105, no. 8, 2014, doi: 10.1063/1.4894217.
- [8] H. Chakrabarti, R. Maity, S. Baishya, and N. P. Maity, "An accurate drain current model of dual material double gate metal oxide

- semiconductor field effect transistor,” *Silicon*, vol. 14, pp. 7235–7243, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12633-021-01321-y.
- [9] S. Pillay and V. M. Srivastava, “Realization with fabrication of double-gate MOSFET based class-AB amplifier,” *International Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering & Telecommunications*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 399–408, 2020, doi: 10.18178/ijeetc.9.6.399-408.
- [10] S. Leeuw and V. M. Srivastava, “Realization with fabrication of double-gate MOSFET based buck regulator,” *International Journal of Electrical and Electronic Engineering & Telecommunications*, pp. 66–75, 2021, doi: 10.18178/ijeetc.10.1.66-75.
- [11] S. Pathania, P. Gupta, R. Kumar, and S. Kumar, “Design and performance benchmarking of dual gate flexible bilayer graphene FETs,” in *2021 IEEE Bombay Section Signature Conference (IBSSC)*, 2021, pp. 1–6, doi: 10.1109/IBSSC53889.2021.9673467.
- [12] A. H. Gambhir and D. M. Bhalerao, “Designing of graphene based MOSFET and comparison of it with generalized MOSFET,” in *2018 International Conference on Circuits and Systems in Digital Enterprise Technology (ICCSDET)*, 2018, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ICCSDET.2018.8821087.
- [13] N. Faizah Z. A., I. Ahmad, P. J. Ker, P. S. Menon, and A. Maheran A. H., “ V_{TH} and I_{LEAK} optimization using Taguchi method at 32nm bilayer graphene PMOS,” *Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering (JTEC)*, vol. 9, no. 2–7, pp. 105–109, 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/235220751.pdf>
- [14] A. Maheran. A. H., Menon P. S., I. Ahmad, and S. Shaari, “Optimisation of process parameters for lower leakage current in 22 nm n-type MOSFET device using Taguchi method,” *Jurnal Teknologi*, vol. 68, no. 4, pp. 45–49, 2014, doi: 10.11113/jt.v68.2987.
- [15] N. Mendiratta and S. L. Tripathi, “18nm n-channel and p-channel dopingless asymmetrical junctionless DG-MOSFET: low power CMOS based digital and memory applications,” *Silicon*, vol. 14, pp. 6435–6446, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12633-021-01417-5.
- [16] S. K. Swain, A. Dutta, S. Adak, S. K. Pati, and C. K. Sarkar, “Influence of channel length and high-K oxide thickness on subthreshold analog/RF performance of graded channel and gate stack DG-MOSFETs,” *Microelectronics Reliability*, vol. 61, pp. 24–29, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.microrel.2016.03.001.
- [17] S. K. Mah, I. Ahmad, P. J. Ker, K. P. Tan, and Z. A. N. Faizah, “Modeling, simulation and optimization of 14nm high-K/metal gate NMOS with Taguchi method,” in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Semiconductor Electronics (ICSE)*, 2018, pp. 275–278, doi: 10.1109/SMELEC.2018.8481293.
- [18] Z. Renthlei, R. S. Dhar, and S. Nanda, “Comparative performance analysis based short channel effects for TG Nano FinFETs,” *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2021, vol. 1921, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1921/1/012014.
- [19] H. Guan and C. Jiang, “Study on the physical and leakage current characteristics of an optimized high-k/InAlAs MOS capacitor with a HfO₂-Al₂O₃ laminated dielectric,” *Coatings*, vol. 8, no. 12, 2018, doi: 10.3390/coatings8120417.
- [20] H. Guan and H. Lv, “Study on leakage current mechanism and band offset of high-k/n-InAlAs metal-oxide-semiconductor capacitors with HfO₂ and HfAlO dielectric,” *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 661, pp. 137–142, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.tsf.2018.07.009.
- [21] M. Khaouani and A. G. -Bouazza, “Impact of multiple channels on the characteristics of rectangular GAA MOSFET,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1899–1905, 2017, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v7i4.pp1899-1905.
- [22] D. Ovali, D. Ağaogulları, and M. L. Öveçoğlu, “Room-temperature synthesis of tungsten silicide powders using various initial systems,” *International Journal of Refractory Metals and Hard Materials*, vol. 82, pp. 58–68, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ijrmhm.2019.03.028.
- [23] M. S. Adhikari, R. Patel, S. L. Tripathi, and Y. Singh, “Design of SOI MOSFETs for analog/RF circuits,” *Indian Journal of Pure & Applied Physics*, vol. 58, pp. 678–685, 2020, doi: 10.56042/ijpap.v58i9.31374.
- [24] A. A. Arpia *et al.*, “Catalytic microwave-assisted torrefaction of sugarcane bagasse with calcium oxide optimized via Taguchi approach: Product characterization and energy analysis,” *Fuel*, vol. 305, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2021.121543.
- [25] Z. A. N. Faizah *et al.*, “Process parameters optimization of 14nm MOSFET using 2-D analytical modelling,” *2nd International Conference on Green Design and Manufacture 2016 (IConGDM 2016)*, vol. 78, 2016, doi: 10.1051/mateconf/20167801017.
- [26] H. Magenthiran and A. M. A. Hamid, “Design and Analysis of 18nm Graphene/HfO₂/WSix NMOS Device Using Taguchi Method,” in *Proceedings of Innovation and Technology Competition (INOTEK)*, 2021, pp. 1–2. [Online]. Available: <https://inotek.utem.edu.my/inotek/article/view/104/70>
- [27] A. H. A. Maheran, P. S. Menon, I. Ahmad, and S. Shaari, “Effect of halo structure variations on the threshold voltage of a 22 nm gate length NMOS transistor,” *Materials Science in Semiconductor Processing*, vol. 17, pp. 155–161, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.mssp.2013.09.009.
- [28] F. A. Anizam, L. N. Ismail, N. Sihab, and N. S. M. Sauki, “Performance of high-k dielectric material for short channel length MOSFET simulated using silvaco TCAD tools,” *Journal of Electrical & Electronic Systems Research*, vol. 19, pp. 143–148, 2021, doi: 10.24191/jeesr.v19i1.019.
- [29] “2013 International Technology Roadmap for Semiconductors (ITRS). Semiconductor Industry Association.” <https://www.semiconductors.org/resources/2013-international-technology-roadmap-for-semiconductors-itrs/> (accessed Oct. 26, 2021).
- [30] V. B. Sreenivasulu and V. Narendar, “Design and Temperature Assessment of Junctionless Nanosheet FET for Nanoscale Applications,” *Silicon*, vol. 14, pp. 3823–3834, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s12633-021-01145-w.
- [31] K. Yang, E. -C. Teo, and F. K. Fuss, “Application of Taguchi method in optimization of cervical ring cage,” *Journal of Biomechanics*, vol. 40, no. 14, pp. 3251–3256, 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.jbiomech.2006.12.016.
- [32] Z. A. N. Faizah, I. Ahmad, P. J. Ker, P. S. A. Roslan, and A. H. A. Maheran, “Modeling of 14 nm gate length n-Type MOSFET,” in *2015 IEEE Regional Symposium on Micro and Nanoelectronics (RSM)*, 2015, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/RSM.2015.7354988.
- [33] H. J. Lee *et al.*, “Intel 22nm FinFET (22FFL) Process Technology for RF and mm Wave Applications and Circuit Design Optimization for FinFET Technology,” *2018 IEEE International Electron Devices Meeting (IEDM)*, 2018, pp. 14.1.1-14.1.4, doi: 10.1109/IEDM.2018.8614490.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Nur Hazwani Naili Mohd Nizam received the B. Aircraft Engineering Technology in Avionics from Universiti Kuala Lumpur Malaysian Institute of Aviation Technology in 2019. She is currently working towards the master degree in microelectronic devices and nanotechnology. Her research interest is in nano electronic and semiconductor devices. She can be contacted at email: m022020001@student.utem.edu.my.

Afifah Maheran Abdul Hamid received the Bac. Deg. of Electronic Engineering and Computer Engineering (Hons.) from Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in 2006 and M.Sc. Degree in Microelectronics from Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM), in 2006 and 2008 respectively. She received the Ph.D. degree in Micro Technology and Nano Engineering from Institute of Microengineering and Nanoelectronics, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM), in 2015. She joined Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in 2009 as a lecturer and is currently a senior lecturer at Faculty of Electronic and Computer Engineering (FKEKK), UTeM. Her research interest includes MOSFET and Nanoscale Design Device Simulation, Statistical Method Optimization and Nanotechnology Variability and Reliability for Robust Design. She can be contacted at email: afifah@utem.edu.my.

Fauziyah Salehuddin is currently an Associate Professor at Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka. She holds a PhD from Universiti Tenaga Nasional. She works at the Department of Electronics & Computer Engineering Technology, Technical University of Malaysia Malacca. Her research of interest is in CMOS design, variability, and statistical modelling. She can be contacted at email: fauziyah@utem.edu.my.

Khairil Ezwan Kaharudin received Ph. D in Electronic Engineering and M. Eng degree in Computer Engineering from Technical University of Malaysia Melaka (UTeM), in 2017 and 2013 respectively. His Ph. D project focused on the process optimization of vertical double gate MOSFET. His research's interests include CMOS design, microelectronics, semiconductors, engineering optimization and artificial intelligence. Recently, his efforts emphasized on the simulation design of Junctionless MOSFET, silicon-on-insulator (SOI) MOSFET, high-k/metal-gate stack technology, design of experiment (DoE) and predictive analytics. He can be contacted at email: khairilezwan@yahoo.com.my.

Noor Faizah Zainul Abidin received Diploma in Electrical and Electronic Engr from Universiti Teknologi Mara while Bachelor degree in Electrical and Electronics Engineering from Universiti Tenaga Nasional and holds master degree in electrical engineering from Universiti Tenaga Nasional. She works at Faculty of Engineering, Limkokwing University of Creative Technology. Her research of interest is in micro and nano electronic and semiconductor devices. She can be contacted at email: faizah.zainulabidin@limkokwing.edu.my.

Anis Suhaila Mohd Zain received the B.Eng. degree in Electrical, Electronic and System Engineering and M.Sc. degree in Microelectronics from Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia (UKM), in 2000 and 2001 respectively. She received the Ph.D. degree in Electronics and Electrical Engineering from University of Glasgow (UK, Scotland), Malaysia in 2013. She joined Universiti Teknikal Malaysia Melaka (UTeM) in February 2002 as a lecturer and is currently a senior lecturer at Faculty of Electronic and Computer Engineering (FKEKK), UTeM. Her research interest includes Nanoscale Device Design and Simulation, Nanotechnology Variability and Reliability of Emerging Technology Devices, IC Design for Biomedical Applications. She can be contacted at email: anissuhaila@utem.edu.my.